

DAMAGE PREDICTION USING ASSOCIATED ACOUSTIC EMISSION FROM COMPOSITE MATERIAL.

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ABSTRACT

The AE event waveforms from a deforming composite material contain a complex combination of frequencies reflecting the damage source mechanisms. It is possible to cluster AE events that have similar characteristics and may also have similar source mechanisms. Using the equations by Ladeveze and LeDantec [1], the stresses retrieved from a finite element model of a composite material are used to calculate the development of damage associated with matrix cracking and fibre debonding. Experimental results from the cluster analysis of AE event data are compared to the results from a theoretical of the accumulation of damage in a composite material.

INTRODUCTION

This work compares the acoustic emission (AE) emanating from a composite material and the predictions of a theoretical damage model. The AE events are grouped according to characteristic waveform parameters. This has separated events originating from differing fracture mechanisms by using a clustering technique, k-means test.

The damage mechanisms occurring in a glass fibre/polyester resin composite material will be due to a complex combination of matrix and fibre dominated fracturing mechanisms. A theoretical model is used which simplifies the composite material structure and allows damage parameters to be calculated to reflect the degree of material degradation. These damage parameters relate to the changes in the transverse and shear moduli as a result of fracture mechanisms reducing the strength of the material.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL TESTING

Composite material was fabricated to have unidirectional fibre orientation. The dry fibres (Silenka E-glass, 2400TEX, as received) were wound on to an open metal frame. The polyester resin (CVP6345.001, MEKP catalyst and cobalt accelerator) was hand impregnated into the fibres, and cured under pressure (50kg/m^2) at 80°C for 10 hours. The specimens were cut to have the fibres at angles of 10° , 20° , and 30° to the loading direction. Tensile testing was performed using Instron and Lloyd testing machines, loading under constant cross-head movement.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION MONITORING

Acoustic emission is the detected stress wave emitted by the composite material due to the impulsive development of damage sites. The released acoustic energy radiates away from the crack tip and is detected at the surface of the specimen as a very small surface movement. It is assumed that since the specimens were relatively small the transit distance for the AE stress wave was short, so the attenuation losses due to internal scattering and absorption and dispersion are minimal. The assumption is that similar mechanisms from different parts of the specimen will be detected as an AE event with comparable waveform characteristics.

The AE transducer was attached to the centre of the composite specimens, using a constant pressure spring clip and ultrasonic coupling gel. The transducer used was resonant at 175kHz. It is assumed that the transducer signal characteristics being evaluated reflect gross differences in fracture source mechanism distinguishable by narrow band transduction. The transducer signal was amplified (30dB 55kHz-550kHz preamplifier AECL). This amplified signal was digitised by an A-D board (1MHz sampling rate, Keithley DAS50) set to be triggered by the voltage level rising above a preset level. Two hundred data points (total time duration 200 s) were sampled per AE event. The sampled event waveform was rapidly stored on computer hard disk via direct memory access.

When the composite was deforming rapidly and the AE rate was high, the maximum rate of capture by the digitising system was about 20-25 events per second. No data capture system can digitise every event emitted, so it has to be assumed that the events captured are a representative selection of the total.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION WAVEFORM ANALYSIS

The AE parameters used included: the peak amplitude (PA) the difference between the maximum to minimum peaks (volts), the ringdown count (RD) the number of positive oscillations above a threshold value, and the risetime (RT) the time from the event start to the largest maximum or minimum peak (milliseconds). Other parameters, such as event duration and the energy were also calculated but not used in any further analysis.

Carrying out a qualitative visual inspection of AE waveforms suggested that there were different types of event occurring at certain times in the experiment. This would agree with our view that different mechanisms were still distinguishable after detection and digitisation.

The AE parameter data was subjected to different mathematical manipulations to extract the similarities and differences in the data. The principal component analysis (PCA) attempts to distinguish variations between the parameters, or variables, for each event. Clustering techniques, such as the k-means relocation or Ward's methods, group events with similar variable relationships into the same cluster.

PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

Principal component analysis reduced the three parameter values to a single number representing the greatest linear variation between the events. The first component had the greatest variation, whilst the second component also had the greatest variation but with the condition that there was no correlation with the first component. These first two components (PC1 and PC2) accounted for the maximum amount of variation between all the events, so if plotted would separate events with different variable values in to distinct regions of the graph.

It was noted that PCA did group events with similar characteristics, but there was no clear demarcations between groups. Rather there was a "boomerang" shaped spread of the results.

CLUSTER ANALYSIS

The same event data was submitted to a mathematical package (CLUSTAN Ltd., UK) for cluster analysis in an attempt to separate and outline groups of events with strong similarities.

The cluster technique used was the k-means test of the Euclidean sum of squares. The Euclidean sum of squares is the sum of the distances between events in a cluster to the centre of the cluster. For an event to belong to a cluster the iterative k-means test removes and replaces events attempting to find the best cluster location that minimises the errors. A limit is set on the number of iterations possible if the calculations do not come to a natural minimum.

Due to the immense number of calculations required, the number of events were restricted to 999 events with three variables (peak amplitude, ringdown count and risetime).

The events were randomly allotted to a cluster at the start of the cluster analysis. The final cluster content did not depend on the event starting cluster. The number of clusters was reduced from 5 to 3 groups with the 4 cluster level reported.

FINITE ELEMENT DAMAGE MODEL

The theoretical model for the development of damage in a composite material, suggested by Ladeveze and LeDantec [1], predicts a level of damage dependant on the stresses experienced and hence the material moduli reductions in a theoretical composite.

Using the method of finite element analysis to segment a model into small volumes, or elements, it is possible to calculate the stress responses at the mesoscale for a loaded composite. The composite material response to subtle changes in the material properties can be studied without the need to fabricate every variation.

Figure 1: Cluster and stress plots for (a) 10°, (b) 20° and (c) 30° composite

The 2-D PAFEC finite element model consisted of 6×48 plane stress orthotropic quadrilateral elements (1 element was approximately 16 mm^2).

The FE model is loaded incrementally and the stresses from each element retrieved and used to calculate the damage values (d and d') for the composite material. These damage parameters d and d' increased as the damaged state developed, affecting both the transverse and shear moduli.

Initial constants for the material before deformation are determined using specimens made of similar fibres and matrix. These constants then control the degree of deformation given the damage calculated at each applied stress level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ACOUSTIC EMISSION DATA

Composite material with three fibre orientations were subjected to the PCA and cluster analyses. These orientations were 10° , 20° and 30° cut from glass/polyester unidirectional composite material.

Cluster 1 AE events were observed to have characteristically small amplitude, few ringdown counts and a short risetime. For the three composite material orientations, (figure 1,(a),(b),(c)) cluster 1 shows a gradual increase in event rate for increasing fibre angle.

For the 10° composite, clusters 2 and 4 are observed to be close together on the PCA plots and are seen to rise together in figure 1 (a). Both clusters have relatively few events until the modulus starts to change, after which both gradually rise.

Cluster 4 for both the 20° and 30° materials has a much more pronounced increase in AE just after the modulus knee. This sharp increase in the AE event rate is also present in the 10° composite (cluster 4 and 2).

The rapid change in the rate of occurrence of clusters 2 and 4 for all three material orientations, highlights a significant change in the way the material is deforming and fracturing. Cluster 2 and the early stages of Cluster 4, could be a general phase of material deformation where matrix cracks experienced in the early stages of testing are coalescing into significant cracks that are now impinging on to the fibre zone - reflected by the changing material modulus.

The first events appearing in cluster 3 occur as the clusters 2 and 4 event rate rises. Cluster 3 events are characteristically large amplitude with many ringdown counts, reflecting fracture processes that release larger amounts of energy than the other AE events.

With the associated modulus change, it would suggest that events in cluster 3 are fibre dependant. The process of fibre breakage and fibre debonding, would release larger amounts of energy than matrix cracking for example. This would agree with the cluster 3 events having larger peak amplitudes and many more ringdown counts.

ALL BLANK SQUARES= 10

Central Element =

Key	d'	d	Key	d'	d
01	0.0	0.1	32	0.3	0.2
10	0.1	0.0	41	0.4	0.1
11	0.1	0.1	42	0.4	0.2
12	0.1	0.2	52	0.5	0.2
21	0.2	0.1	73	0.7	0.3
22	0.2	0.2	84	0.8	0.4
			100	failed	

Figure 2: A selection of finite element meshes containing damage parameters.

DAMAGE MODEL

For a composite material that has fibres at off angle inclinations to the loading direction, the mechanisms will involve the matrix as well as the fibres. Since the stronger fibres are no longer in pure tension, but have transverse and shear stresses acting, the interface region and the matrix will also contribute to the fracture mechanism. The damage parameters increase to reflect the damage developed at each stress load level applied.

The initial change in the state of the elements was for the d' damage parameter to increase to 0.1 (damage value = 10). This reflected a small decrease in the transverse modulus. This transverse modulus damage could be analogous to the widespread matrix cracking experience in testing composite materials at low stress levels.

At the higher stress levels the damage zone around the central element spreads out towards the specimen edges. The values for d' and d increase indicating that damage involves not only the pure transverse matrix cracking, but also the fibre debonding damage involving shear and transverse stresses. The matrix cracking has coalesced to form significant cracks that intercept the fibres and debond the matrix from the fibres.

The stress level in the finite element model was increased to 7.0 MPa, at which point the damage calculations would not stabilise even after 11 attempts at this load. The damage continued to grow. This may be the limit for this theoretical model.

CONCLUSION

The finite element damage model demonstrated the progression of damage through the mesh. The central element acted as the stress concentration with damage progressing from this point towards the sample edges.

AE events were clustered using k-means clustering method. The AE event clusters show differing response as composite samples with increasing fibre orientation are subject to stress. Certain of these clusters appear sensitive to sample modulus change. The number of events occurring in certain clusters at specific points in the tests, can be taken as highlighting the differing modes of failure in the material.

The FE damage model and AE waveform analyses do show similarities with regard to the response to stress with few AE events during the initial stage of loading and little response from the damage model. Work is continuing to relate the evolution of AE to the increase in the damage parameter.

REFERENCES

- 1 Ladeveze, P and LeDantec, E, "Damage modelling of the elementary ply for laminated composites", *Composite Science and Technology* 43 (1992) 257-267.

